

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

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D3.5 – Seeds or plant material of advance breeding material to be used in WP4

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Type

- R** Document, report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
- OTHER**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public
- CO** Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Deliverable 3.5

Based on the performance of different crops in previous projects we have selected a set of varieties for testing in WP4 of lignocellulosic crops and oil crops for different locations in Europe:

1. Miscanthus: new experimental miscanthus hybrids developed by Wageningen University (WU) have been made available for the MAGIC consortium. University of Hohenheim (UHOH) have established field trials in 2018 and INRA is planning field trials for 2019/2020
2. Hemp: varieties of hemp with good fibre quality and high contents of CBD have been made available to the MAGIC consortium by Van Dinter Semo (VDS). UHOH set up field trials with the variety Markant in 2018. This variety was not suited for the condition in South of Italy so University of Catania (UniCat) used a better suited variety from an Italian Breeder
3. Crambe: Crambe seeds of the variety Galactica have been made available to the consortium by Wageningen Research (WR). Field trials have been set up at University of Bologna (UniBo) and CRES.
4. Camelina: Seeds of camelina have been made available to the MAGIC consortium by WR and CRES, including the Midas variety. A field trial was set up in 2018 at UHOH.

Apart from the exchange of the material mentioned above, other species have been made available to the consortium, that can be used for field trials in 2019/2020 (Table 1)

Table 1: Additional material available for the MAGIC consortium

Partner	Species	Varieties	Quantity available
LSFRI Silava	Willow	Visvaldis Monika, Emma, Estere, Bella, Wilhelm, Birgit.	200 propagules
LSFRI Silava	Poplar	Vesten + some new clones	900 propagules
LSFRI Silava	Black locust	Frost tolerant variety	Seeds for 1000 trees
CRES	Camelina	Midas	5 kilos
CRES	Crambe	Galactica	900
CRES	Castor	Six hybrids	200 gr seed of each hybrid
CRES	Switchgrass	Kanlow	1 kilo